

Teachers' Perceptions regarding Code-Switching and Code-Mixing ...

Teachers' Perceptions regarding Code-Switching and Code-Mixing as Scaffoldings in Teaching L2 Speaking Skills at Graduation Level

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Abstract

The prime objective of this research was to investigate English language teachers' perceptions regarding code-switching and code-mixing as scaffoldings in teaching L2 speaking skills of the BS students enrolled in different public and private universities and colleges of Multan and Bahawalpur Districts. This article was completed by employing the quantitative data analysis approach. 250 male and female English language teachers responded positively during the academic calendar of 2021. Questionnaire was the tool for data collection that was structured in which the respondents were requested to specify their level of endorsement or disagreement on four-point rating scale. The results and findings of the study data indicated that all the teachers were unanimously agreed and said "Yes" on all the statements of the questionnaire. The evaluated data disclosed that English language teachers disclosed that code-switching and code-mixing in L2 classrooms has favorable impacts on L2 teaching and learning. Results of this article also show that English language teachers' code-switching and code-mixing help them to pass the information to the students easily. Additionally, most of the teachers also agreed and delivered a highly positive attitude regarding code-switching and code-mixing as they feel that their students feel relaxed and happy during teachers' code-switching/ code-mixing in L2

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atmosphere. The reason behind this concept is as teachers' code-switching and code-mixing decreases the pressure of L2 language on B.S English students. In addition to this approach, English language teachers' code-switching and code-mixing make L2 learners bilingual rather multilingual.

Keywords: Bilingualism, Code-Switching, Code-Mixing, Teachers, Learners.

1. Introduction and Background of the Study

In the last decades, second language teaching approach has evolved to include socio-linguistic, discourse, and strategic competency as part of the framework of actual L2 communication, rather than focusing primarily on grammatical competence. However, similar to a metaphoric pendulum swing, this progress was aided in part by the teacher and students' widespread dislike of any classroom L1 use. "English Only" became the rule. Numerous scholars have reconsidered their positions on classroom L1 code switching and code mixing through recent years. There is growing acknowledgment that using L1 for L2 instruction has a number of advantages. Native language code switching and code mixing can help L2 instruction advance more quickly on the initial and beginning levels by serving help across the complete spectrum of classroom circumstances.

1.1 Role of Only in English in L2 Classroom

In respect to both abroad teaching of EFL and domestic education of ESL, the monolingual "English Only" method has not always been the standard in the teaching of English to speakers of other languages (Baron, 1990; Crawford, 1991). In fact, it is important to stress at the beginning that there have always been recurring swings in American education policies, which were more often than not dictated by political rather than educational causes. Local bilingual education was made possible by the dispersed and nearby controlled structure of 19th century community education, which permitted for local bilingual education in accordance with the political power – and, thus, linguistic alignment – of a region's ethnic composition (Auerbach, 1993). At the turn of the twentieth century, a resurgence of nativism and anti-foreign political sentiment faced a sudden decline in domestic bilingual education, and, ensuing the outburst of World War I, the urban convergence of increased migration from Southern and Eastern Europe, as well as an important role in the nascent labor movement, subsidized to a progressively xenophobic atmosphere (Crawford, 1991). As a result, the Americanization movement gained traction during that time period, blaming foreign influences for the country's political and economic woes. Consequently, learning English as a second language is a good way for a worker to show commitment to both the firm and the country (Baron, 1990). In this atmosphere, the "English Only" classroom strategy arose, with its basic concept encouraging students to utilize L2 English as their primary mode of communication between instructors and classmates. As a result, the grammar-translation technique was widely discredited, including the abandonment of Contrastive Analysis or CA in language education (Atkinson, 1987), and the direct method or DM gained admiration, with special second language use apparently boosting requiring code exposure and hence maximizing knowledge (Eldridge, 1996; Sampson, 2012). As a result, "English Only" turn out to be the de facto standard in American ESL programs (Baron, 1990), with adult ESL training focusing increasingly solely on practical

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English over the initial few periods of the 20th century, such as instructions on how to sign up a bank account, consult a doctor, navigate directions, make purchases, and express thanks. Henry Goldberger's educational recommendations, developed as an instructor in the New York City Public School system, are a renowned example of this fledgling ESL teaching style. Goldberger recommended that EL be used exclusively in the classroom and instructed teachers to "avoid the establishment of 'national cliques,' which would standstill the work of Americanization" (Baron, 1990).

For the intention of enhancing American ideals and barring foreigners from the levels of the education sector, established turnstile methods, such as residency rules and language and articulation exams for teacher licensing, became a part of the teacher selection process (Auerbach, 1993). "As a consequence to homogenize the language of the teaching corps, educationists remained by and large monolingual speakers of the English Language unskilled in any given technique to teach English to non-anglophones and therefore disable to connect with the non-anglophone learners," writes Baron (1990). This has been observed that "English Only," would become a core concept in CLT in the upcoming periods of the mini century (Meiring and Norman, 2002; Butzkamm, 2003), also confirmed to be a comfortable technique for the growing quantities of inborn English-speaking instructors travelling abroad to pursue work in English language teaching with very restricted or no control of the learners' L1 (Macaro 2005), as well as for ELT publishers (Butzkamm, 2003; Sampson, 2012). Since the 1880s, most teaching approaches have avoided the LI by using the Direct Method. "The monolingual principle, the distinctive services of the 20th century to classroom language teaching, remains the core assumption from which the others ultimately flow," writes (Howatt, 1984).

Phillipson (1992), for example, looked at frequently held ideas about ELT methodology that arose during British neo - colonial strategies towards the end of the twentieth century, and he contends that the creation of ELT as a profession was also a direct reaction to political need. In the late 1950s and early 1960s, the EL viewed in a critical organization chart of Britain's neo - colonial authority, and financing for English Language Teaching was supplied. Activities that are taken for free as pedagogically sound have their origins in blatantly ideological impulses with the important exception that the sociopolitical objective has undoubtedly the more explicit drive behind "English Only" in the English as Second Language classroom at the time.

1.2 Code Switching and Code Mixing

According to Redouane (2005), the first description of code switching was given by Weinreich (1953), who characterized bilinguals as those who transfer from one language to other depending on appropriate variations into the spoken context. In 1980s, code switching or code swapping had become a well-known phenomenon and teaching approach among instructors (Shay, 2015). Code switching, also known as "code mixing," "code changing," or "code shifting," is the act of moving between two languages inside a single discourse, sentence, or element (Piasecka, 1988). In the nineties, scholars began to pay more attention to the areas in which code flipping could aid interpersonal communication activities among instructors and learners in bilingual classrooms in the U. S. The first code switching research focused on the effects of code switching in bilingual instructors' communication and the

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degree with which diverse languages, mainly English and Spanish, were used to execute distinct properties (Martin-Jones, 1995). From that, scholars have increased the dimensions of their investigation to add L1 use as part of L2 instruction as well as expanding the geographic scope to encompass bilingual and multilingual academic situations all over the entire globe (Greggio & Gil, 2007).

Nonetheless, once upon a time in the history when native language aversion was not accepted as a social fact, and even a small percentage of people in each era denied it (Cook, 2001). Since the turn of the century, there has been an active argument about whether fluctuating back and forth between L2 and native L1 in an L2 classroom is beneficial or hindering (Jingxia, 2010; Shay, 2015). Wong-Fillmore, as illustration, observed in 1985 that students who were used to observing the instructor using the L1 likely to neglect the L2 and thus missed out on crucial and Comprehensible input. With growing scrutiny over the decades, several researchers have maintained that the Second language should be taught completely in the L2 and that instructors must focus on making a pristine foreign language atmosphere since they're the learners' only linguistic prototypes (Chaudron, 1988; Lightbown, 2001). "The systematic alternating employment of two languages or language variations within a single discourse or speech," according to Lightbown (2001). Nonetheless, Lightbown, an expert in L2 acquisition, advocated for an intralingua method of instruction, thinking that only immersion to the chosen language (L2) could assist students to succeed, with teachers having accountable for supplying this pristine foreign language atmosphere. Furthermore, as Lightbown points out, code switching will only pave the way to disastrous shift in the L2 second language.

Furthermore, the writers believed, learners do not require to comprehend each and everything the instructor uttered, and that code switching in learning a foreign language could lead to undesirable transfers. Switching to the L1 impairs the learning process, according to these researchers, while educating exclusively in the L2 has various advantages, including establishing the language genuine and allowing students to encounter uncertainty. The American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages (ACTFL) suggested in 2010 that "language teachers and learners utilize L2 as extensively as practicable (Ninety percent or more) during teaching time also, where feasible, further than the class" at all levels of instruction (ACTFL, 2010). The ACTFL's suggestion is backed up by a large body of evidence discusses the usefulness of using the target language exclusively, or almost exclusively, to enhance Learners' expertise in L2.

1.3 Limitations of Code Switching and Code Mixing

In order to increase knowledge of a language, Krashen (1985) advocated for the learners' native language or L1 restricted to be utilized in the learning forums. As we've observed, study data accumulated since that time shows that students have a good stance regarding on use of Mother tongue in the classroom in the form of code switching and code mixing, with the condition that overuse of code switching and code mixing can harm the growth of L2 language abilities. Instructors' language switching when diverting pupils from the lecture might be disruptive, therefore employ precaution when using Mother tongue in the classroom. Excessive usage has the potential for negative consequences, as evidenced by a variety of situations. To begin with, students consider English to be an important second

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language, and the English as a foreign language classroom would be the desired location where they can absorb and enhance their knowledge of the English language. Instead of understanding to think in the target language, learners' L2 cognitive ability might be evaluated if they rely on translation from L1 to L2, leading them to believe that they have not "really" grasped any language until it has been interpreted. Narayan (2019) observed that learners in Japan had a negative opinion of professors' code flipping, which could impede L2 acquisition. The instructor's code switching impaired the students' perception of the lecture's fluency and broke the rhythm that was necessary for more comprehensive L2 knowledge on their behalf. The instructor and/or learners may not be able to distinguish between form equivalence, semantic equivalence, and pragmatic aspects, leading to oversimplification and the use of rough and erroneous interpretations. The instructors' switching code has been criticized for impairing the flow of the lesson and disrupting the impetus essential for student learning. Learners may miss out opportunities to strengthen their L2 listening abilities if the instructor switches codes in the class. Participants speculated that this could have a direct and detrimental impact on learners' language, particularly in the areas of talking, hearing, and lexicon. Learners may not recognize that it is critical that they utilize just the topic L2 during many class discussions, instead communicating with instructor in their mother tongue as a subject of routine, in a situation when they can perfectly be able to express themselves in the target language. As a result, code switching has a negative impact on learners' linguistic abilities as well since affective qualities, as learners may feel it extremely difficult to confront a general L2 crowd due to a lack of acquaintance to the L2 (Atkinson,1987; Ellis, 2015; and Fareed, 2016). The current study also deals with the hypotheses L2 teachers have affirmative attitude and perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom. Likewise, teachers' code-switching/code-mixing in English language classroom has positive impact on L2 learners.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Questions of the Research

This article uses two main research questions to find out the answers:

1. What are L2 teachers' perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom?
2. What is the impact of English language teachers' code-switching/code-mixing in English language classroom?

2.3 Research Hypothesis

1. L2 teachers have affirmative attitude and perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom.
2. Teachers' code-switching/code-mixing in English language classroom has positive impact on L2 learners.

2.4 Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate L2 teachers' perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom.
2. To explore the impact of English language teachers' code-switching/code-mixing

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in English language classroom.

2.5 Delimitation of Present Study

A number of limitations were imposed for the conduction of this article, as listed below:

- i. L2 teachers' perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom at graduation level.
- ii. The respondents of this research article were male and female English language teachers.
- iii. These teachers were teaching English at BS, MA, MPhil & PhD at the public and private universities and colleges of Multan and Bahawalpur Districts.
- iv. Multan and Bahawalpur Districts were selected for the collection of the required data.
- v. Research was restricted to the departments of English of the said institutions of the Punjab.

2.6 Impact of the Study

It is significant to mention that this research is an endeavor to determine teachers' perceptions regarding code-switching and code-mixing as scaffoldings in teaching L2 speaking skills at graduation level and the prominence of this research curtailed from the following inspections:

- i. This article explores teachers' perceptions regarding code-switching and code-mixing as scaffoldings in teaching L2 speaking skills at graduation level
- ii. Data from this study scrutinizes L2 teachers' perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom.
- iii. This study would subsidize the impact of English language teachers' code-switching/code-mixing in English language classroom.

2.7 Research Sites

The sites from which the data was collected were the public and private universities and colleges of Multan and Bahawalpur Districts where BS in English is being taught.

2.8 Information about the Participants

The respondents of this research were male and female English language teachers. These teachers were teaching English at BS, MA, MPhil & PhD at the public and private universities and colleges of Multan and Bahawalpur Districts.

2.9 Design of the Current Study

This article was completed by employing the quantitative data analysis approach. Selected locations of the research were the public and private universities and colleges of Multan and Bahawalpur Districts. 250 male and female English language teachers responded positively during the academic calendar of 2021. Questionnaire was the tool for data collection that was structured in which the respondents were requested to specify their level of endorsement or disagreement on four-point rating scale, including Yes, No, No Idea and No Comments. Teachers' questionnaire was the data collection technique and it was developed from the studies by Moiiinvaziri, M., (2008), Shirkey, D., (2003), Huang, C., (2007), and Alonso, Rocio Segura (2012) as models.

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3. Teacher's Responses Analysis (Questionnaire Wise)

Table 3.1 Do your students demand you to use your native language in ELT classroom?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	230	92.0	92.0	92.0
No	19	7.6	7.6	99.6
No Idea	1	.4	.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.1 shows the importance of code switching/code mixing in ELT classroom and it also discloses that the target language teachers were requested to show their level of likeness or difference on a Four-Point assessment scale of Yes, No, No Idea, and No Comments. As indicated in the table above, the analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 230 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that there is a great need to use the native language/s in the form of code switching and code mixing in ELT classroom and this number carries 92% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 230 remains same as 92%. Among the 250 respondents, 19 target language teachers revealed that they prefer to use their mother tongue interchangeably in ELT settings as a facilitating tool and this number carries 7.6% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 19 target language teachers is 7.6 One teacher of 250 target language teachers reported that he/she has "No Idea" regarding the use of mother tongue in foreign language classroom setting and this sole number has only 0.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0 as no one reported that he/she has "No Comments" in this first table of this project.

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Fig-1: Do you think that in the ELT classroom there is a need of mother

Do you think that in the ELT classroom there is a need of mother tongue?

Table-1 and Fig-1 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do your students demand you to use your native language in ELT classroom?” 92% believed “Yes” while 7.6% responded in “No” while only 0.4% had “No Idea”.

3.2 Do you think that in ELT classroom there is a need of code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	232	92.8	92.8	92.8
No	16	6.4	6.4	99.2
No Idea	1	.4	.4	99.6
No	1	.4	.4	100.0
Comments				
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

As indicated in the table above, the analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 232 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that there is a need of

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code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons and this number carries 92.8% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 232 remains same as 92.8%. Among the 250 respondents, 16 target language teachers revealed that they do not prefer to use their L1 interchangeably in ELT settings and this number carries 6.4% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 16 target language teachers is 6.4 and cumulative percentage rises to 99.2. One teacher of 250 target language teachers reported that he/she has “No Idea” regarding the need of code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons and this sole number has only 0.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 99.6. Similarly, just one L2 teacher reported no one reported “No Comments” in this second table of this project. This only number has only 0.4% of the total number and its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0.

Do you think that in ELT classroom there is a need of code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons?

Percent

Do you think that in ELT classroom there is a need of code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons?

Table-2 and Fig.-2 shows that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that in ELT classroom there is a need of code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons?” 92.8% believed “Yes” while 6.64 responded in “No” while only 0.4% had “No Idea” and 0.4% replied in “No Comments”.

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3.3 Do you think that code switching can be adopted as tool for L2 learners in the ELT classroom?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	233	93.2	93.2	93.2
No	16	6.4	6.4	99.6
No Idea	1	.4	.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

As indicated in the table above, the analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 233 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that code-switching and code-mixing can be adopted as tool for L2 learners in the ELT classroom and this number carries 93.2% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 230 remains same as 93.2%. Among the 250 respondents, 16 target language teachers revealed that cannot be adopted as tool for L2 learners in the ELT classroom and this number carries 6.4% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 16 target language teachers is 6.4 and accumulative percentage is 99.6. One teacher of 250 target language teachers reported that he/she has “No Idea” regarding code-switching and code-mixing as tool for L2 learners in the ELT classroom and this sole number has only 0.4% of the total number and its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0.

Do you think that code switching can be adopted as tool for the L2 learners in the ELT classroom?

Table-3 and Fig.-3 indicates that when the respondents were asked “do you think that code-

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switching and code-mixing can be adopted as tool for L2 learners in the ELT classroom?" 93.2% believed "Yes" while 6.4% responded in "No" while only 0.4% had "No Idea".

3.4 Do you think that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	212	84.8	84.8	84.8
No	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

As shown in the table 3.4 the analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 212 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom and this number carries 84.8% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 230 remains same as 84.8%. Among the 250 respondents, 38 target language teachers revealed that they do not think that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom and this number carries 15.2% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 38 target language teachers is 15.2 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0.

Do you think that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom?

Do you think that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom?

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Table-4 and Fig.-4 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom?” 84.8% believed “Yes” while 15.2% responded in “No.”

3.5 Do you think that there is a need of code switching and code mixing to communicate with the L2 learners in ELT classroom?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	218	87.2	87.2	87.2
No	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The analyzed data in the table 3.5 revealed that among the 250 respondents 218 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that there is a need of code switching and code mixing to communicate with the L2 learners in ELT classroom and this number carries 87.2% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 230 remains same as 87.2%. Among the 250 respondents, 32 target language teachers revealed that there is a no need of code switching and code mixing to communicate with the L2 learners in ELT classroom? and this number carries 12.8% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 32 target language teachers is 12.8 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0.

Do you think that there is a need of code switching to communicate with the teachers in the ELT classroom?

Do you think that there is a need of code switching to communicate with the teachers in the ELT classroom?

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Table-5 and Fig-5 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom?” 87.2% believed “Yes” while 12.8% responded in “No”.

3.6 Do you think that code switching and code mixing can assist your L2 learners in writing an application?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	171	68.4	68.4	68.4
No	72	28.8	28.8	97.2
No Idea	1	.4	.4	97.6
No Comments	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

As indicated in the table above, the analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 171 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that they think that code switching and code mixing can assist their L2 learners in writing an application and this number carries 68.4% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 230 remains same as 68.4%. Among the 250 respondents, 72 target language teachers revealed that they do not think that code switching and code mixing can assist their L2 learners in writing an application and this number carries 28.8% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 28.8 and accumulative percentage is 97.2. One teacher of 250 target language teachers reported that he/she has “No Idea” regarding code switching and code mixing as an assistive tool for their L2 learners in writing an application and this sole number has only 0.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 97.6. 6 out of 250 teachers reported that they have “No Comments” in this table of the project and this number carries 2.4% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 2.4 and accumulative percentage is 100.0.

Do you think that code switching can assist you in writing an application?

Do you think that code switching can assist you in writing an application?

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Table-6 and Fig.-6 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that code switching and code mixing can assist your L2 learners in writing an application?” 68.4% believed “Yes” while 28.8% responded in “No” while only 0.4% had “No Idea” and 2.4% had responded in “No Comments”.

3.7 Do you think that code switching and code mixing can assist your students in writing the summary of the lesson?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	219	87.6	87.6	87.6
No	25	10.0	10.0	97.6
No Idea	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.7 indicated in that out of 250 respondents 219 reported that they think that code switching and code mixing can assist their students in writing the summary of the lesson and this number carries 87.6% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 219 remains same as 87.6%. Among the 250 respondents, 25 target language teachers revealed that they do not think that code switching and code mixing can assist their students in writing the summary of the lesson and this number carries 10.0% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 25 target language teachers is 10.0 and accumulative percentage is 97.6. Only 6 teachers of 250 target language teachers reported that they have “No Idea” regarding code switching and code mixing as an assistive technique for the learners in writing the summary of the lesson and this number has only 2.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 2.4 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0 as no one reported that he/she has “No Comments” in this table of the project.

Do you think that code switching can assist you in writing the summary of the lesson?

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Table-7 and Fig.-7 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that code switching and code mixing can assist your students in writing the summary of the lesson?” 87.6% believed “Yes” while 10.0% responded in “No” while only 2.4% had “No Idea”.

3.8 Do you think that code-switching and code mixing can assist your L2 learners to understand the lectures?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	212	84.8	84.8	84.8
No	36	14.4	14.4	99.2
No Idea	1	.4	.4	99.6
No Comments	1	.4	.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

As indicated in the table above, the analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 212 reported that they think that code-switching and code mixing can assist L2 learners to understand the lectures delivered in the class and this number carries 84.8% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 212 remains same as 84.8%. Among the 250 respondents, 36 target language teachers revealed that they do not think that code-switching and code mixing can assist L2 learners to understand the lectures and this number carries 14.4% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 36 target language teachers is 14.4 One teacher of 250 target language teachers reported that he/she has “No Idea” regarding this and this sole number has only 0.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 99.6 and only one reported that he/she has “No Comments” in this table of this project and this sole number has only 0.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 0.4 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0

Do you think that code-switching can assist you to understand the lectures of your teachers?

Do you think that code-switching can assist you to understand the lectures of your teachers?

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Table-8 and Fig.-8 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that code-switching and code mixing can assist your L2 learners to understand the lectures?” 84.8% believed “Yes” while 14.4% responded in “No” while only 0.4% had “No Idea” and similarly 0.4% replied, “No Comments.”

3.9 Do you think that code-switching and code-mixing can assist your students during the presentation of the topic in the classroom?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	157	62.8	62.8	62.8
No	12	4.8	4.8	67.6
No Idea	81	32.4	32.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.9 Indicated that among the 250 respondents 157 reported that code-switching and code-mixing can assist the students during the presentation of the topic in the classroom and this number carries 62.8% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 157 remains same as 62.8%. Among the 250 respondents, 12 target language teachers revealed that code-switching and code-mixing cannot assist the students during their presentation on any topic in the classroom and this number carries 4.8% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 12 target language teachers is 4.8 and accumulative percentage is 67.6. 81 teachers of 250 target language teachers reported that they have “No Idea” in this regard and this number has only 32.4% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 32.4 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0.

Do you think that code- switching can assist you during the presentation of the topic in the classroom?

Table-9 and Fig.-9 indicates that when the respondents were asked “Do you think that code-switching and code-mixing can assist your students during the presentation of the topic in

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the classroom?" 62.8% believed "Yes" while 4.8% responded in "No" while only 32.4% had "No Idea".

3.10 Do you think that code switching and code mixing can assist your L2 learners in reading activities during classroom?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	187	74.8	74.8	74.8
No	46	18.4	18.4	93.2
No Idea	17	6.8	6.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 3.10 shows that among the 250 respondents 187 reported that they think code switching and code mixing can assist their L2 learners in reading activities during classroom and this number carries 74.8% of the total number. Valid and cumulative percentage of the number 187 remains same as 74.8%. Among the 250 respondents, 46 target language teachers revealed that they do not think that code switching and code mixing can assist L2 learners in reading activities during classroom and this number carries 18.4% of 250 target language teachers and valid percentage of 46 target language teachers is 18.4. 17 teachers of 250 target language teachers reported that they have "No Idea" regarding the use of code switching and code mixing as an assistive device for L2 learners in reading activities during classroom and this sole number has only 6.8% of the total number. Its valid percentage is 6.8 and the accumulative percentage is 100.0 as no one reported that he/she has "No Comments" in this table.

Table-10 and Fig.-10 indicates that when the respondents were asked "Do you think that code switching and code mixing can assist your L2 learners in reading activities during classroom?" 74.8% believed "Yes" while 18.4% responded in "No" while only 6.8% had "No Idea".

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4. Findings and Discussions of the Research Questions

4.1 Research Question# 01

What are L2 teachers' perceptions regarding the use of code-switching /code-mixing in L2 classroom?

Findings of the ELT teachers' questionnaire indicated that most of the teachers are highly motivated to use native languages such as Urdu, Punjabi and Siraiki in their L2 classroom extensively in various situations. The analyzed data revealed that among the 250 respondents 230 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that there is a great need to use the native language/s in the form of code switching and code mixing in ELT classroom and this number carries 92% of the total number. Similarly, data revealed that among the 250 respondents 232 reported a high agreement among the teachers and they perceive that there is a need of code-switching and code-mixing to make the learners understand the theme of difficult lessons and this number carries 92.8% of the total number. Likewise, among the 250 respondents 212 reported a high agreement among the teachers that there is a need of code switching and code mixing to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom and this number carries 84.8% of the total number. Furthermore, among the 250 respondents 212 reported that there is a need of code switching to understand the difficult phrases of English language in the ELT classroom and this number carries 84.8% of the total number. Moreover, among the 250 respondents 218 reported that there is a need of code switching and code mixing to communicate with the L2 learners in ELT classroom and this number carries 87.2% of the total number. Additionally, 171 out of 250 respondents reported that they think that code switching and code mixing can assist their L2 learners in writing an application and this number carries 68.4% of the total number. In the same line of action, out of 250 respondents 219 reported that they think that code switching and code mixing can assist their students in writing the summary of the lesson and this number carries 87.6% of the total number. Among the 250 respondents 212 reported that they think that code-switching and code mixing can assist L2 learners to understand the lectures delivered in the class and this number carries 84.8% of the total number. Further, the context is strengthened when 157 out of 250 respondents reported that code-switching and code-mixing can assist the students during the presentation of the topic in the classroom and this number carries 62.8% of the total number. Similarly, among the 250 respondents 187 reported that they think code switching and code mixing can assist their L2 learners in reading activities during classroom and this number carries 74.8% of the total. From the above-mentioned findings, it can be maintained that the use of code-switching and code-mixing by English language teacher in L2 classroom often happens either due to specific drive or instinctively. It logically supports and benefits L2 learners to comprehend the communication transported and in conclusion learners can realize the objectives of L2 learning.

4.2 Research Question# 02

What is the impact of English language teachers' code-switching/code-mixing in English language classroom?

The results and findings of the study data indicated that all the teachers were unanimously

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agreed and said "Yes" on all the statements of the questionnaire. The evaluated data disclosed that English language teachers disclosed that code-switching and code-mixing in L2 classrooms has favorable impacts on L2 teaching and learning. According to the current research discoveries about the impacts of teachers' code-switching and code-mixing on teaching and learning process in L2 classroom, responses articulated from the teachers are in "Yes." It shows that L2 teachers contemplate the role of code-switching and code-mixing as highly positive and constructive regarding L2 pedagogy at BS level in the two prominent districts of the south Punjab as it is because L2 teachers reflect that the use of code-switching and code-mixing is dynamic as it keeps back time and makes L2 teaching and learning process easier and facilitating. Correspondingly, teachers also think that code-switching and code-mixing provide them a well-organized and exact means for investigating and comparatively investigating various semantic structures and typologies of words and their suitable use in miscellaneous contexts in the foreign language and it assists as a kind of perceptive backing for serving them to remember what they had cultured beforehand.

5. Conclusion

Result of this article shows that English language teachers' code-switching and code-mixing help them to pass the information to the students easily. Additionally, most of the teachers also agreed and delivered a highly positive attitude regarding code-switching and code-mixing as they feel that their students feel relaxed and happy during teachers' code-switching/ code-mixing in L2 atmosphere. The reason behind this concept is as teachers' code-switching and code-mixing decreases the pressure of L2 language on B.S English students. In addition to this approach, English language teachers' code-switching and code-mixing make L2 learners bilingual rather multilingual.

6. Pedagogical Implications of the Study

1. English language teachers' code-switching and code-mixing can be supportive among L2 learners through evolving and improving their linguistic difficulties.
2. Much of the listening practice and philological performances can upgrade the level of understanding among students by the use of English language teachers' code-switching and code-mixing in the foreign language classroom.
3. By the use of code-switching and code-mixing English language teachers can avoid the use of difficult vocabulary and they can set their L2 learners relaxed so that they can comprehend the point easily.

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